

**LEGAL BASIS OF CONCLUSION OF INSURANCE CONTRACTS
USING THE INTERNET****Boltaev Mansurjon Sotivoldievich,**

Tashkent State University of Law,

Dosen of Civil Law Department,

Doctor of legal sciences

E-mail: beshkap0721@gmail.com

ANNOTATION: The globalization of the electronic economy has led to significant growth in the world market of business services. Recent advances in information technology and the Internet have changed the perception of business technology and usage boundaries. The rapid growth of information technology opens up new opportunities and creates new challenges for Internet insurance. The saturation of traditional commodity markets requires the consumer to constantly look for new approaches.

Keywords: nsurance, Internet, contract, insured, insurer, insurance company, insurance services, insurance policy.

In the modern world, any self-respecting company that works for its image has a corporate website. It is much more convenient for potential customers to learn about the products and services they are interested in while sitting at a computer than by calling on the phone or visiting the company's office. The number of services provided by various financial institutions on the Internet is constantly growing. After banks providing remote account services to their customers using online banking, many insurance organizations are increasingly paying attention to the Internet and showing their willingness to provide online insurance services.

Introduction of electronic document circulation and Internet insurance system, further development of existing customer service systems in the world market and centralized management of newly established Internet insurance portals are of urgent importance. Today, the relevance of internet insurance is related to the development and global spread of computer networks and their use in various fields. Computer networks have become the primary means of communication and business for millions of people.

Internet insurance is an insurance contract that includes choosing an insurance product, calculating the rate and insurance amount, signing a policy, and making a payment through an

insurance company's website or an insurance intermediary. 'direct drafting' is the arrangement of the insurance inspection and delivery of the paper form of the policy (if required by the terms of the insurance).

Many works on the subject of Internet insurance of professional liability were developed by foreign experts: G. Caprio, S. Kol, A. Demirgus-Kant, I. Kirsner, A. Operkentlar. Their research provides a basis for understanding the Internet purchasing system in individual countries, each of which is characterized by a certain degree of financial services market development and historical aspects of online commerce.

A review of Internet purchasing systems in foreign countries conducted by scientists from these countries allows us to observe the laws of operation of Internet insurance systems based on statistical and historical and political aspects. American researchers prefer data protection systems in already functioning Internet interaction complexes. Western European scientists study the US experience and create a unique model of Internet portals. The works of Eastern European scholars are dominated by theoretical information about the introduction of Internet purchasing systems and the consideration of foreign experience.

Internet insurance is one of the forms of purchase activity of an insurance company, because the saturation of classic channels for the distribution of insurance services requires the creation and development of new, cost-effective and convenient mechanisms for interaction with customers . In order to comprehensively study the operation and development of Internet insurance systems in foreign countries, it is necessary to refer to the economic nature of this concept and the principles of its organization.

The current state of development of the insurance market is characterized by the rapid automation of business processes and the transition to cloud and Internet technologies. The use of the Internet as a new channel for the distribution of insurance products allows at the same time to facilitate their acquisition by customers and reduce the cost of purchasing insurance services for the insurance company. Reducing the costs of the insurance company through e-commerce does not affect the quality of services, and the customer receives the same economic benefits as in the traditional approach.

The rapid growth of the number of Internet users has been the main factor in the transformation of the insurance market into a high-tech structure that requires more and more practical developments. Changes have begun in the effective model of building business processes. Fundamental changes have occurred in the behavior of individual consumers and in the insurance segment as a whole.

Insurance as a financial service has an intangible nature - it is considered a suitable object for sale without direct contact between the seller and the buyer. First of all, it applies to insurance types that do not require the physical presence of the insurer's representative to assess the property interests to be insured. So, this post is all about the types of insurance with low premiums, fixed insurance rates and premiums [1].

A comparative method was used to determine the characteristics of Internet insurance in foreign countries, which made it possible to use geographically diverse studies and get a complete picture of the phenomenon.

The development of Internet technologies is an undeniable stage in the development of modern society. Free high-speed access to a wide range of 3G and 4G networks from a variety of smart devices means that consumers are able to perform all their daily network tasks anywhere and anytime with less time wasted. These conditions give rise to many debates about online commerce and its relation to conventional methods of distribution of goods and services.

Over the past three decades, direct sales have dominated the "robot", modern research shows the growing role of e-commerce in the capitalization structure of many companies, as live communication and communication with people is the main factor in increasing the volume of sales.

The human element of service relationships cannot be completely ignored, but in many cases, reducing the time spent on routine administration and customer service operations is a positive for both insurance companies and their customers.

One of the reasons for the growth of the Internet insurance market in developed countries is the increase in demand for self-service systems. Undoubtedly, the main examples of what can be called Internet banking, self-service checkouts in supermarkets, indicate the significant popularity of "using the system" with your own hands. The main reason for rejecting additional staff and performing certain operations by the client is the ability to avoid queues and the ability to perform individual operations at the time and place that is necessary and convenient for the client [2].

The development of self-service in the insurance industry, more than one million customers of BGL have been able to manage their insurance contracts via the Internet, confirmed by data from Junction. A similar situation was observed at Ageas Insurance Solutions, which is considered the largest representative of the auto insurance industry. Its customers have switched to self-service through Auto Direct, managing their contracts through the insurance company's website. Since the launch of this service, more than 97% of customers have switched from paper

to electronic documents.

It is unreasonable to ignore this level of demand for self-service systems. There is a particular need to implement Internet technologies in a price-sensitive market with large, powerful players.

One of the most dynamic representatives of online insurance is car insurance in the UK, where two-thirds of the market contracts online. In this sector, in the context of a gradual decrease in the level of premiums, the volume and efficiency of attracting customers comes to the fore. In such circumstances, it is more effective to use websites that offer competitive pricing policies and self-service options [3].

User interface development has become one of the main tasks for insurance companies, because the general perception of the product depends on it. The latest self-service portals are designed with both telephone and direct sales experiences in mind. With each update, they feature increasingly sophisticated designs and functionality that meet both insurance company goals and consumer preferences [4].

Following the trends that started with the launch of iOS 7 and Windows 8, all websites have started to use simple interfaces that make them as easy as possible for self-service.

The benefits of self-service are becoming increasingly apparent. For customers, this is an opportunity to more conveniently exchange information and manage individual processes, that is, to meet the needs of the most demanding customers. Also, this principle of working with customers allows them to feel more actively involved, because at any time they can visit their "office" on the insurance company's website or through a mobile application, and this does not require coming to the office, and sometimes even is easier and more convenient than calling.

Significant cost reductions and efficiency gains for the insurance company or broker, including reduced costs of paper document storage and speeding up individual business processes. In particular, the electronic submission of documents by clients and their automatic attachment to their personal records reduces the time spent on conducting business with clients and confirms the timeliness and completeness of the information provided, which can be a key factor in the resolution of individual disputes [5].

85% of policyholders can complete more than 85% of transactions without asking for help from insurance company employees. This relieves insurance company employees from routine activities such as searching and managing documents and evidence in insurance cases. In such conditions, employees can deal with non-standard insurance cases, VIP customer service and development of individual insurance protection conditions.

Controlling bodies are moving to electronic document circulation. Currently, state bodies are completely reforming the paper policy and switching to the electronic version of documents. To combat fraud, a centralized database has been created to verify the validity and legitimacy of each insurance policy.

Intrente technologies have undoubtedly opened a new page for the development of insurance fraud, but their use allows to speed up the verification of information from other sources and databases from the client.

Large software to obtain a single software product and database that can be implemented in the online trading technologies of insurance companies and brokers of individual players of the information and insurance market, such as IIL (Insurance Initiatives Limited) and LexisNexis started interactions with developers.

Such a product allows you to get complete information about the client in real time. Such verification allows the participants of the insurance market to eliminate potential fraudsters who demand compensation from insurance companies for non-existent losses or deliver them intentionally. A special functionality of this solution is to quickly formulate a tariff policy for honest customers and calculate additional rewards and bonuses for them.

Self-service systems also create a unique, personalized online footprint that can be used by insurance companies and brokers to access and research individual customer information. This information allows us to offer individual insurance solutions, additional options for existing contracts, and to formulate ongoing customer requirements for the operation of online systems.

Recent developments and research allow insurance market representatives to access so-called "big data". Their research and systematization allows for a more complete picture of the behavioral aspects of the activities of each individual customer and their groups, which means that it creates a potential opportunity to better meet customer requirements, improve existing ones, and develop new products. According to researchers at Amazon and Spotify, information about already purchased items can more effectively suggest potential purchases to customers to complement or improve the operational features of their existing ones [6].

Changes in the field of online insurance allow the simulation and automation of normal business processes. Such changes allow to reduce labor costs for management of insurance cases and management of compensation processes, to reduce the number of mandatory contacts with representatives of insurance structures for the client, and to facilitate the management of their insurance policies.

To date, there are more than 4,800 insurance companies in the United States that have

their own online offices.

According to recent studies, the annual Internet turnover of the global insurance market is \$ 800 million, which is 8-10% of the total Internet sales. Currently, 7% of insurance companies' revenues are accounted for by e-commerce. According to the forecasts of the auditing firm PricewaterhouseCoopers, this indicator will reach 22% in 2023. And the share of insurers that communicate with their customers online and attract new ones will grow from 11 percent to 70 percent during this period. Given the dynamics of Internet access in general, this forecast is quite reasonable.

In the United States, in addition to the websites of individual companies, there are also specialized insurance portals. On the websites of portals (www.insweb.com, Insure.com, insurance.com, lifeshopper.com, etc.) they collected information about the largest players in the insurance market. The user can compare the prices of different insurers for the same type of services, find out what is included in certain insurance services of a certain company. You can also familiarize yourself with the ratings of insurance companies compiled by the largest agencies and portal creators. An additional convenience for the client is the availability of "geographical distribution". A visitor to the portal can find out the best offers for any insurance applicable in their state.

There are also mini-portals that combine 2 to 10 companies operating in one or different sectors of the insurance market. These portals unite project participants into a single virtual insurance system, according to which the client can buy a policy online. Thus, the client is offered many different insurance products on one site. And usually, first the potential policyholder is asked to choose the desired insurance program, and then the company. Examples of such portals include QuickenInsurance Universal Portal (which combines Travelers, Electric Insurance, Reliance Direct and Ohio Casualty Groups) and eHealthInsurance (Kaiser Permanente, PacifiCare, Blue Cross/Blue Shield and Health Net).

Usually, on the company's personal websites or mini-portals, visitors are advised to register, that is, fill out a form with personal data and, if only one type of service is offered on the site, which can be used when applying information is provided for insurance purposes.

Below are 2 companies that sell their services entirely online. Despite the fact that almost every American insurance company has its own website, many of them prefer to offer their services through Internet brokers - insurance portals [7].

American International Group, Inc. A leading US-based international insurance organization and one of the largest underwriters of commercial and industrial insurance in the

Americas. Its member companies provide various types of insurance in about 130 countries (including Russia and Ukraine). As of the end of 2022, AIG ranked first among all organizations specializing in insurance and financial services in the United States and 17th among all American public corporations in terms of net profit. AIG's strong financial position is reflected by the highest credit rating (AAA) according to leading international rating agencies such as "Moody's" and "Standard & Poor's".

AIG's main Internet presence is the www.aig.com portal, which provides access to other company sites. The website www.aigcorporate.com has been established to provide general information about the Corporation and its divisions. Here the history of AIG is described in detail, news related to the company's activities are presented, the visitor can get acquainted with all the main annual financial reports, etc.

A special website - www.aigdirect.com (only for US residents) was created for individuals and small business entities to sell their services online. It offers the following types of insurance: car insurance, property insurance, life insurance, accident insurance and travel insurance. A special section of the website has been created for each type of insurance, which includes a description of the service and possible types of payment for it. Each department also has a customer service center: answers to common questions, an insurance glossary, expert advice, and more. Each service has its own insurance calculator, where the buyer can choose not only the insurance parameters, but also the type of premium payment (one-time or in installments), the calculation interest rate, certain may calculate the amount of insurance premium depending on the tax collection etc. in one country. The most comprehensive and content-rich section is the section dedicated to car insurance, even practical driving tips, information on vehicle protection systems such as ABS, ESP, Air Bags, etc. there is. All this is presented in the form of high-quality video recordings.

The process of buying a policy for any type of insurance looks pretty much the same. It is divided into 5-7 stages, during which the buyer must answer some questions or fill in the relevant web forms. First, the buyer's country of residence is determined. Then 4-5 questionnaires are filled out, in which the buyer enters information about the conditions of the insurance program he needs, the insurance object, the method of making payments, etc. . The last step is to enter personal information about the client: address, phone number, e-mail address and plastic card number for receiving the insurance premium. After that, the insurance policy is created and sent to the customer by mail. In the process of applying for the purchase of an insurance policy, the buyer cannot calculate the amount of the insurance premium. Therefore,

before submitting the application, he should calculate this amount in the insurance calculator.

It is also possible to request an insurance event on the website by filling out the appropriate questionnaire [8].

Internet insurance is a set of interacting elements that allow the distribution and management of insurance contracts over the Internet. Developing such a system of interaction with customers has a number of advantages and disadvantages, in which the company will have the opportunity to expand its business by selling insurance services online. Each insurance company should independently choose the options and mechanisms for creating online insurance in order to improve its competitive position and eliminate possible shortcomings.

The combination of Internet insurance implementation options allows each company to choose such an algorithm of interaction with the client, which has the opportunity to use existing resources and requires reasonable investments of new ones. The ability to choose the algorithm of interaction with the client via the Internet eliminates the barrier to entry into the online insurance segment.

From the point of view of electronic insurance, the structure and conditions of insurance will be different. Insurance companies specializing in a certain type of insurance can be no less successful than universal insurance corporations, because business efficiency provides strong information support. Information highways will be the basis of future communications. The Internet has already become the main tool and source of the information highway. The change in the field of human business activity, which is called cyberspace, leads to a change in the purpose of the personal computer. From an additional tool, he became an authorized representative of the client of the insurance company. It can be seen that the successful formation of a unified information space of insurance activity requires the compatibility of various highways.

The experience of foreign countries shows the need to develop Internet insurance, because the increase in the number of users and the increase in trust in online systems leads to a sharp increase in the flow of money on the Internet. The following can be pointed out as positive trends of Internet insurance activities in foreign countries: reduction of customer service costs; expanding the territorial coverage of insurance products; improvement of insurance culture; creating self-service opportunities; reducing the influence of the human factor. In this, the model of interaction between the insurer and customers on the Internet is described and it is determined that the structure and conditions of insurance in the conditions of electronic insurance are different.

References:

1. Bazylevich V.D. Insurance: Textbook./ V.D. Bazilevich - K.: Znannia, 2008. - 1019 p.
2. Operkent A. Global Economy & Electronic Commerce/ A. Operkent – London: Business School Press, 1999.
3. Market of financial services: education. manual / S.V. Naumenkova, S.V. Mishchenko and others. - K.: Znannia, 2010. - 532 p.
4. Kirzner I. Competition and Entrepreneurship / Kirzner I. – Chicago, 1973. – 523 p.
5. Rasshivalov D. Intermediary services in insurance / D. Rasshivalov // Bulletin of Taras Shevchenko Kyiv National University. Economy. / Kyiv National University named after Taras Shevchenko. - Kyiv, 2008. - Vol. 106. - pp. 35-37.
6. Wholesale distribution of internet-insurance for human use //Official Journal of the European Communities EN – L113 – 30.04.1992 – [Електронний ресурс]. Режим доступу: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/oj/direct-access.html>.
7. Market of financial services: education. manual / S.V. Naumenkova, S.V. Mishchenko and others. - K.: Znannia, 2020. - 532 p.
8. Tlusta G., Erastov V. Foreign experience of functioning and development of Internet insurance // Bulletin of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv. Economics, 2015, 3(168): 55-62 p.
9. Sotivoldievich, B. M. (2023). LEGAL ISSUES OF IMPROVING HEALTH INSURANCE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. American Journal of Business Management, Economics and Banking, 15, 130-136.
10. Boltaev, M. S. (2021). Problems Use of Compulsory Health Insurance. International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding, 8(10), 489-495.